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FINAL REPORT**1 | General information****DFG reference number:** STE 3139/1-1**Project number:** 493936649**Project title:** Invasive rat impacts on insular invertebrate biodiversity: investigating the selective mechanism of rat predation and the taxonomic and functional implications for island ecosystems**Name of the applicant:** Dr Sebastian Steibl**Official address:** School of Biological Sciences, University of Auckland Waipapa Taumata Rau, 3 Symonds St, 1010 Auckland, Auckland, Aotearoa New Zealand**Name of the host individual and institution:** Prof Dr James C. Russell, School of Biological Sciences, University of Auckland Waipapa Taumata Rau, Auckland, Aotearoa New Zealand**Reporting period (entire funding period):** 01 Mar 2022 to 28 Feb 2024 (24 months)**2 | Zusammenfassung / Summary****2.1 | Deutsche Zusammenfassung**

Invasive Arten sind die größte Bedrohung für die Biodiversität auf Inseln. Vor allem invasive Ratten (*Rattus* spp.) sind dort hauptverantwortlich für das Artensterben. Während deren Auswirkungen auf Vögel ausführlich dokumentiert sind, bleiben deren Effekte auf Wirbellose – sowie der Mechanismus für selektive Prädation – weitgehend unbekannt. In diesem Walter Benjamin-Projekt wurden Theorien aus der Ernährungsökologie genutzt, um den Mechanismus für den selektiven Prädationsdruck von invasiven Ratten auf Wirbellose zu identifizieren, und funktionelle Folgen für Inselökosysteme zu bewerten.

Die Nährstoffaufnahmeziele invasiver Ratten wurde durch Wahlversuche unterschiedlichen Proteingehalts ermittelt. Entgegen der Erwartung eines einheitlichen artspezifischen Zielwerts strebten 84% der Tiere einen Proteingehalt von 10,7% an, während 16% bei 43,5% Protein lagen. Statistische Analysen bestätigten zwei Aufnahme-strategien. Folgeuntersuchungen zeigten, dass die „High Protein“-Population überwiegend aus adulten Männchen und fortpflanzungsaktiven Weibchen bestand, was darauf hinweist, dass Körpergröße, Geschlecht und physiologischer Zustand den Proteinbedarf erhöhen. Laufende Laboranalysen werden diese Zusammenhänge weiter beleuchten.

Um diese Versuchsergebnisse mit Felddaten zu unterstützen, erfolgte eine DNA-Metabarcoding Analyse der Mageninhalte von invasiven Ratten. Die relative Häufigkeit von Tier- gegenüber Pflanzen-DNA spiegelte die Wahlversuch-Cluster wider: Rund 85% der Ratten nahmen wenig Tiernahrung (<25%) auf, während 15% bis zu 92% hoch-proteinhaltiges

Tiermaterial im Magen hatten. Ein zweite invasive Rattenart konsumierte insgesamt mehr tierische Nahrung, wobei der Tiernahrungsanteil signifikant mit Körpergröße und Geschlecht korrelierte.

Eine geplante inselweite vollständige Entfernung der dortigen invasiven Rattenpopulation sollte im nächsten Projektabschnitt Vorher-Nachher-Vergleiche ermöglichen, die die Erholung von Invertebraten und deren ökologischer Funktionen quantifizierte. Der Eingriff zur Rattenentfernung blieb jedoch erfolglos. Stattdessen wurde deswegen ein räumlicher Vergleich zwischen Inseln mit und ohne invasive Ratten gewählt, um korrelative Unterschiede in der Invertebraten-gemeinschaft zu quantifizieren. Die Anwesenheit invasiver Ratten hatte negative Auswirkungen auf verschiedene ökologische Wirbellosen-Funktionen; der Anteil natürlicher Waldfläche erwies sich jedoch als stärkerer Einflussfaktor für die Funktionalität des Inselsystems.

Die Ergebnisse dieses Projekts liefern ein mechanistisches Modell zur Prädation invasiver Ratten auf Insel-Wirbellose, basierend auf unterschiedlichem Proteinbedarf. Sie sind für das Management invasiver Arten relevant, da sie eine Doppelausrichtung der Fresspräferenzen und damit der Köderwirkung aufzeigen. Momentan laufende Analysen im Anschluss an dieses Projekt werden kausale Zusammenhänge festigen und robuste Modelle selektiver Nahrungswahl sowie wirksamere Schutzmaßnahmen ermöglichen.

2.2 | English summary

Biological invasions are the predominant threat to island biodiversity. Among island invaders, rats (*Rattus* spp.) are especially harmful, being responsible for 30% of recorded extinctions. While their impacts on island birds are well documented, effects on invertebrate communities – and the mechanisms driving selective predation – remain poorly understood. This Walter Benjamin project applied theoretical advances in nutritional ecology to test the mechanism for selective predation pressure on invertebrates, and to assess consequences for ecosystem functioning.

Nutrient intake targets of invasive rats (*R. exulans*) were quantified. Contrary to expectations of a single, species-specific intake target, 84% of tested animals aimed at a 10.7% protein intake target, while 16% balanced at 43.5% protein. Statistical analysis confirmed two distinct intake strategies. Follow-up measurements showed that the high-protein group consisted of large adult males and breeding females, suggesting that body size, sex, and physiological state elevate protein demand. Ongoing laboratory analyses will further clarify these links.

To relate nutrient intake target findings to natural foraging, metabarcoding on rat stomach contents from an invaded island site were conducted. Sequencing read abundances of animal (high-protein) versus plant material (low-protein) mirrored feeding-trial clusters:

roughly 85% of *R. exulans* showed low animal intake (< 25% of sequencing reads), whereas 15% displayed up to 92% animal content. *R. rattus* consumed more animal matter overall, with a significant correlation between animal diet prevalence and rat size and sex.

An island rat eradication operation was initially planned to be utilised by this project for investigating the recovery trajectories of island invertebrate communities in relation to the nutrient intake target matching, and for quantifying recovery of arthropod-mediated ecological functions. This operation was unsuccessful, thus precluding before-after comparisons. However, two years of systematic invertebrate sampling generated a dataset on island invertebrate community dynamics, turnover, and stability. Using a space-for-time design across islands (8 invaded, 4 rat-free), trait-based functional analysis revealed effects of invasive rat presence on invertebrate functioning. Herbivore and decomposer functions were reduced under rat presence, although native forest cover emerged as the stronger predictor for overall invertebrate functional integrity.

Together, the results of this project advance a mechanistic, generalizable framework for invasive-rat predation on island invertebrates, rooted in differential protein demands by invasive rats. The findings have relevance for invasive species management, indicating duality in feeding preferences and, thus, bait attractiveness. Completion of follow-up analyses will solidify causal pathways, enabling robust models of invasive rat foraging and more effective conservation interventions.

3 | Scientific progress report

3.1 | Background and objectives of the project

Oceanic islands occupy just 7% of Earth's surface yet support 20% of its biodiversity and nearly half of all threatened species [1]. While islands face many disturbances, biological invasions – especially by rats (*Rattus* spp.) – pose the greatest threat [2,3]. Rats have established on 90% of archipelagos and caused 30% of recorded extinctions. Their impacts on native birds are well documented, but effects on invertebrate communities, and the drivers of selective predation, remain poorly understood [4], leaving two critical knowledge gaps.

First, it has been shown how rat-driven declines in island birds disrupt nutrient cycles, seed dispersal and other ecosystem functions that birds naturally fulfil [5,6]. Similarly, invertebrates fulfil numerous ecological functions on islands (e.g., pollination, herbivory, leaf litter decomposition) [7], yet the impacts from invasive rats on invertebrate-mediated ecological functioning in island systems remain largely unexplored [8].

Second, although case studies report persistence or decline of particular island invertebrate taxa under rat presence [4], no general mechanistic framework explains why rats target some groups but avoid others. This limits transferability: rat predation pressure recorded in one geography may not apply to systems with different invertebrate assemblages [9].

This Walter Benjamin project was aimed at addressing these gaps by (i) testing for the mechanism of selective rat predation on island invertebrates and (ii) quantifying the impacts of invasive rats on arthropod functioning in island ecosystems. For identifying a selective predation mechanism, the project adopted the nutritional-geometry framework, which posits that each species forages to meet a fixed macronutrient intake target, *i.e.*, a species-specific ratio of carbohydrates, lipids and proteins [10,11]. By determining invasive rats' macronutrient intake target and comparing them with the nutrient profiles of different invertebrate taxa (for example, lipid-rich bugs versus protein-rich grasshoppers [12]), it was aimed to develop a mechanistic, generalizable model for predicting which invertebrates are most vulnerable to rat predation. The three objectives of this research project were to:

1. Identify the nutrient intake target of invasive rats through feeding trials and match the identified intake target with rat stomach content data from DNA metabarcoding.
2. Utilise an island rat eradication operation to quantify whether the early response of island invertebrate communities to the removal of invasive rats can be predicted based on the matching between rat intake target and invertebrate nutrient composition.
3. Quantify early responses and recovery of island invertebrate functions to rat removal.

3.2 | Project-specific results and findings

3.2.1 | Nutritional intake targets (work package “a. selective mechanism”)

The limiting macronutrient for invasive rats, and driving force for their detrimental predation pressure, was expected to be proteins [13]. Therefore, to determine the intake nutrient target of invasive rats, two standardised pellet bait mixes were manufactured, each consisting of an equicaloric (14.5 MJ/kg net metabolizable energy [NME]) mix but differing in the percentage of protein-derived NME (5% NME protein vs. 45% NME protein).

Remarkably and contrary to literature expectations, the tested invasive rat population did not converge on a single protein nutrient intake target. Instead, while 37 out of 44 individuals (*ca.* 84%) converged at an intake target of $10.7 \pm 6.3\%$ protein (9.646 ± 5.469 kJ/day from protein), seven out of 44 individuals (*ca.* 16%) had an elevated protein nutrient intake target of $43.5 \pm 2.1\%$ protein (50.771 ± 15.093 kJ/day from protein) (Fig. 1). Cluster analysis confirmed the presence of two distinct intake targets (K-means: $R^2 = 0.453$, $k = 2$).

At this early stage in the project, the findings already substantially deviated from the project's initial hypothesis (and literature) of a singular, species-specific intake target. Given that this promising finding challenged previous research on nutritional geometry and entailed management-relevant implications, it was decided together with the host and collaborators (incl. David Raubenheimer, a world-leading expert in nutritional ecology) to further disentangle the bimodal intake target in invasive rats.

Figure 1: Bimodal nutrient intake target of Polynesian rats. Panel on left shows the mean daily energy intake from protein relative to the energy intake from carbohydrates and lipids. Panel on right shows the relative intake target for proteins and total net metabolizable energy (NME) uptake. Colour point with error bars indicates the population-level centroid of low-protein target (orange) and high-protein target (blue) rats with standard deviations. Dashed ellipse indicates the 95% confidence interval at the population level.

Follow-up measurements on rat physiological status and morphometrics were conducted. All tested rats of the ‘high protein’-cluster were identified to be large-bodied, adult animals, 5 out of 7 of which being males (Fig. 2A). Strong statistical support was found that the interactive effect of male sex and large body weight is increasing the protein intake target (Bayesian regression: $\beta = 0.28 [-0.04 - 0.58]$ mean effect and 95% credible interval of posterior slope; Posterior Probability PP ($\beta > 0$) = 93%). Hormonal status and hierarchy may modulate protein demand in rodents [14]. The preputial gland size was identified as a capable proxy to dominance status and hormonal levels in male rats [15], and subsequent analysis revealed that the relative preputial gland size was correlated with an elevated protein intake target (Bayesian regression model: $\beta = 4.98 [0.30 - 10.13]$; PP ($\beta > 0$) = 96%) (Fig. 2B). The two female rats with a high protein nutrient intake target were both lactating, *i.e.*, in breeding. Several other physiological factors, including testes size or presence of stomach parasites were found to be unrelated to the bimodal protein intake target. At the time of completion of this Walter Benjamin project, follow-up analyses were still ongoing, including stable isotope analysis of different tissues with different turnover times. Direct hormonal level measures on frozen blood samples from each rat are also under planning. When these laboratory analyses will be completed (aim summer 2025), they will provide a stronger evidence base to test the hypothesis that a bimodal response in protein demand is driven by physiological status, at which stage a scientific manuscript for peer-reviewed publication will be prepared.

Figure 2: Predictors for the elevated protein nutrient intake target. A: rat body weight (x-axis) and sex (colour-code) were identified as partially explaining an increased protein intake target. B: Within the large-bodied, adult males, the relative preputial gland size was identified as a strong correlate with increased protein intake target.

To relate the observed nutrient intake targets in the feeding experiments with real-world foraging data, metabarcoding of rat stomachs was conducted. Stomach content samples were obtained from Polynesian (*R. exulans*) and Ship rats (*R. rattus*) from the same invasive population that was used for the nutrient intake experiments and analysed using quantitative (qPCR) metabarcoding sequencing [16,17].

Relative sequencing read abundances between plant (low-protein) to animal (high-protein) amounts revealed similar patterns to the nutrient target experiments. While ca. 85% of Polynesian rat stomachs contained only a low relative read abundance of animal OTUs in their stomachs (<25%), 8 out of 55 (ca. 15%) contained up to 92% animal OTUs in the

Figure 3: Relative sequencing read abundance of animal OTUs in the stomachs of rats. Each data point indicates the stomach content of one rat species, red lines are linear regression with grey ribbons indicating the 95% credible interval.

stomach. Ship rats displayed an overall higher relative contribution of animal material than Polynesian rats, with heavier individuals and, particularly, heavier females showing a strongly increased relative contribution of animal OTUs to their diet ($\beta_{weight} = 0.26$ [0.01 – 0.52]; PP ($\beta > 0$) = 95%; $\beta_{weight \times female} = 0.35$ [0.08 – 0.61]; PP ($\beta > 0$) = 98%) (Fig. 3). Once follow-up stable isotope analysis will be complemented, the findings of the metabarcoding data will be integrated into the resulting manuscript for a multi-methodological, and potentially high-impact publication on the bimodality in invasive rat predation behaviour.

3.2.2. | Connect rat intake targets to early responses of invertebrate communities to rat removal (work package “b. taxonomic impacts”)

The macro-nutritional composition of key prey items that were either found in the metabarcoding analysis or were known to be present on the field site were calculated and summarised in a right-angle mixture triangle (Fig. 4). Using the atoll-wide rat eradication operation at the field study site, the next goal was to test whether changes in the invertebrate community following removal of rats can be related to the relative matching between an invertebrate species' nutritional geometry and the intake target(s) of rats. For field sampling, a total of 96 invertebrate trapping stations were distributed across Teti'aroa

Figure 4: Right-angle mixture triangle for prey items of invasive rats on tropical atoll systems.

Atoll (French Polynesia) to repeatedly collect atoll-wide invertebrate community composition data over the two-year time span of this Walter Benjamin project. However, and problematically to the original concept of the project, the eradication of rats became first delayed into mid-2022 due to COVID-pandemic caused disruptions and was then confirmed a failed operation as rats survived on all islands.

Even though a temporary suppression of invasive rats was achieved, rats were found to be breeding again beginning October 2022 suggesting population recovery and ongoing predation pressure. No measurable effect of this temporary suppression on invertebrate species richness or invertebrate biomass were detected (Fig. 5). However, the two-year sampling generated an unprecedented dataset on the temporal dynamics in invertebrate communities on remote tropical atoll island systems, that allowed other fundamental ecological insights into compositional turnover, impacts of seasonality, and ecological stability (see section 3.3 and manuscript in appendix). In addition, this two-year dataset now constitutes a major knowledge basis for pre-eradication conditions that can be leveraged in future projects following the second eradication attempt in 2025.

Figure 5: Island invertebrate community response to temporary suppression of invasive rats over a two-year monitoring period. Colour codes depict individual islands on which invasive rats were present at the beginning of the project and attempted to become eradicated; vertical, red dashed line indicates the time of the attempted rat eradication operation (Jun/Jul 2022). Invertebrate species richness (A) measured on the plot-level for each island; invertebrate biomass (B) measured cumulatively across all plots per island.

3.2.3 | Evaluate recovery trajectories of invertebrate-mediated functions (work package “c. functional implications”)

Given the unsuccessful rat eradication operation, the original project plan to evaluate recovery trajectories of invertebrate ecological functions could also not be realised. However, due to the spatial configuration of the field site – a coral atoll consisting of $n = 12$ individual islands, of which only eight islands were invaded – a space-for-time approach was possible to compare invertebrate functional diversity on islands with and without invasive rats.

Invertebrates were assigned into functional groups using trait databases [18]. The data was then integrated into a large, multi-author analysis that holistically compared the impacts of invasive rats on the studied atoll ecosystem across the land-sea interface (seabirds, forest, invertebrates, lizards, coral reefs, marine productivity) in a space-for-time approach (Graham et al. in prep.). To unlock a comparative metric across this taxonomically diverse dataset, an ecosystem energetics approach was adopted [19]. Energetics approaches measure how much metabolizable energy (beginning from plant primary productivity) is flowing into different ecosystem compartments and functions. For invertebrates, the interaction between higher native forest cover and the presence of seabirds (a reciprocal measure for rat status, *i.e.*, absence of rats) jointly modulated the allocation of ecosystem energy flows into invertebrates and core invertebrate-mediated functions (predation, herbivory, and decomposition). These findings show that rat invasions on atoll islands have significant ramifications for the realisation of invertebrate-mediated functions. However, relative to invasive rat presence, the condition of the island forest itself (low vs high native vegetation cover) emerged as the more influential predictor for increased ecosystem energy allocation into invertebrate functioning.

3.3 | Deviations from the original concept

This two-year Walter Benjamin project experienced significant deviations from its original concept, both due to unexpected yet promising empirical findings that contradicted literature and original hypotheses (work package a), and due to a failed rat eradication operation, which should have provided the conditions for investigating invertebrate recovery trajectories in relation to rat nutrient intake target matching (work package b) and through the lens of ecosystem functioning (work package c).

Unlike expected, the nutrient intake target work and metabarcoding analysis did not reveal a singular intake target and consistent macronutrient balancing in the invasive rats' diets. Instead, a bimodal target was identified. Additional time was allocated into disentangling this bimodality, which was found to be correlated to rat physiological status. Downstream fundings for follow-up analyses were unlocked to corroborate these initial findings that hormonal level and/or dominance status in invasive rats is causing bimodality in intake targets. This decision was made because the findings of bimodal intake targets have significant, management-relevant implications for invasive species management. Baits for rat eradication operations are currently based on a low-protein bait pellet matrix. However, the bimodal intake target findings suggest a dual mix of both low- and high-protein pellets may increase attractiveness for rats at the population level, increasing success of rat eradication operations. Importantly, it was found that large-bodied adult male rats disproportionately survived the eradication attempt at the field site, indicating a possible link between the bimodal intake target findings of this project and the reason of failure for the eradication operation.

Due to the failed operation, the original concept of investigating recovery trajectories was no longer possible. Instead, a space-for-time approach was chosen to compare invertebrate functioning between rat-infested and rat-free islands. While the invertebrate community did not show any measurable changes to the temporary suppression (Fig. 5), the two-year dataset of an island invertebrate community was used to analyse temporal turnover and community stability, and a manuscript is currently in preparation for publication.

3.4 | Description of the handling of research data

This project generated new empirical data through a combination of behavioural experiments (nutritional intake targets), laboratory analysis (metabarcoding), and fieldwork sampling. Generated data types comprise DNA sequences, community-ecological quantitative data on the diversity and abundance of invertebrates, as well as quantitative data on the intake target selection choices of invasive rats. Fieldwork yielded preserved invertebrate specimens.

All bioinformatics and statistical analyses were implemented in R [20], ensuring full reproducibility. While some sequence data and barcodes remain under analysis, they will be

deposited in GenBank upon publication. All scripts and raw data will be released via an open-access Figshare repository provided by the host institution (University of Auckland).

Collected invertebrates are stored in 90% ethanol p.a. at -20°C at the Teti'aroa Atoll research station. Additional voucher specimens have been shared with Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research (New Zealand) for integration into reference collections of Pacific island insects. Rat stomach content samples are archived at UC Berkeley. No restrictions on publication or data access are anticipated. The fellowship recipient will finalize curation of any remaining unpublished data and code following FAIR principles for transparent scientific data management once all findings have been formally accepted for publication [21].

3.5 | Bibliography

[1] Fernández-Palacios JM *et al.* (2021) *Glob Ecol Conserv* 31: e01847. [2] Steibl S (2023) Invasive species, impacts and distribution of. *in: Encyclopaedia of Biodiversity* (ed Scheiner SM), 3rd Edition, Academic Press, US, pp. 636-50. [3] Turbelin AJ *et al.* (2017) *Glob Ecol Biogeogr* 26: 78-92. [4] St Clair JJH (2011) *Biol Conserv* 144: 68-81. [5] Graham NAJ *et al.* (2018) *Nature* 559: 250-53. [6] Heinen JH *et al.* (2023) *Nat Comm* 14: 1019. [7] Losey JE, Vaughan M (2006) *BioScience* 56: 311-23. [8] Vanbergen AJ *et al.* (2018) *Nature Ecol Evol* 2: 16-25. [9] Ruscoe WA *et al.* (2013) *Conserv Biol* 27: 74-82. [10] Shik JZ, Dussutour A (2020) *Trends Ecol Evol* 35: 691-703. [11] Raubenheimer D (2011) *Ecol Monogr* 81: 407-27. [12] Rumbold BA, Schlüter OK (2013) *Molec Nutr Food Res* 57: 802-23. [13] Erlenbach JA *et al.* (2014) *J Mammal* 95: 160-68. [14] Dijkstra H *et al.* (1992) *Physiol Behav* 51: 961-68. [15] Brown JC, Williams JD (1972) *Mamm Rev* 2: 105-47. [16] Zarzoso-Lacoste D *et al.* (2013) *Mol Ecol Res* 13: 117-27. [17] Deagle BE *et al.* (2019) *Mol Ecol* 28: 391-506. [18] Hörren T *et al.* (2022) bioRxiv <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.01.25.477751>. [19] Malhi Y *et al.* (2022) *Nature* 612: 707-13. [20] R Core Team (2023) *R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria*. [21] Wilkinson MD *et al.* (2016) *Sci Dat* 15: 160018.

4 | Publication of project results

Under review

Graham NAJ, Benkwitt CE, Lange ID, Perry CT, Thomson ER, Wedding LM, Dunn RE, Steibl S, Stuart CE, Jeannot L-L, Appoo J, Fillol JR, Stuhr M, Palola P, Carr P, DeVore J, Ducatez S, Zora A, Hastings AK, Barroso SF, Evans S, Schulze M, Cotton E, Reddington H, Malhi Y (*in preparation*) Atoll island resilience enhanced by seabirds and native vegetation.

In immediate preparation

Steibl S, Russell JC. An atoll is an island mosaic of distinct diversity equilibrium points.

Planned for 2025 upon completion of downstream analysis

Steibl S, Graham N, Ringler D, Roderick G, Raubenheimer D, Russell JC. Big rats with big appetite for island birds: bimodal intake targets in invasive rats towards high-protein prey choices driven by physiology.